

Impact of Curriculum in Education

Mrs. S. Sabitha Shunmuga Priya, Ph.D Research Scholar, Research Centre of English, VHNSN College, Virudhunagar.

Dr. R. Kabilar, Associate Professor, Research Centre of English, VHNSN College, Virudhunagar.

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Introduction

A curriculum is an important form of specification in the educational idea. It has the uniqueness of each classroom setting. It has the central defining feature. It should be directed towards an examination as an objective without loss of quality. It means that the examination of a particular course must be in march to pursue other aspiration. In many respects a curriculum in practice and practical development of the process model. These process models should be in the pace of judgment and meaning-making. It may be used as a continual reference to the progress of human spirit and welfare. Thus the action of the curriculum is an informed and committed format which is in usage.

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Introduction

It creates a critical pedagogy which goes beyond situating the learning experience within the experience of the learner. This curriculum creates a process of experiences on both the learner and the teacher. The progress is through dialogue and negotiation which encourages the students and the teachers together to conform to the real problems of their life and career. The curriculum is not simply a set of planning a course, it is a growth in which planning, acting and evaluation are all reciprocally related and mingled into the process. It has done in three ways such as informed and committed and action.

The practice cannot be done in individuals; it gives careful attention to understanding which supports on practice and it proceeds structural questions. A curriculum can explore its experience in a mixture of a different culture, racial groups in society and so on. As a result, it is easy to see the curriculum is focusing on individual attitude. The curriculum has expected to practice with the learners and peers. So make a curriculum many important basic things should be taken to plan the curriculum and the curriculum planning has divided according to the time of a course.

Good Planning

Planning a curriculum boosts confidence in a teacher to handle the class effectively. It gives a meaningful thing to communicate to the pupils. The term of teaching sequence is

Planning \longrightarrow Lesson \longrightarrow Assessment

The planning needs three different timescales. They are long term, medium term and short term.

Long-Term Planning

It covers a lengthy period such as school education. In this long term planning it is to

consider the continuity and progression and coherence of the curriculum. For this type the designer should ask himself/herself about the consideration to extend the each stage of curriculum. The designer should reinforce what pupils have learnt before; what would build on and develop their learning; introduction of new elements and prepare pupils for future learning.

Medium-Term Planning

It is to ask the designer whether a wide enough range of learning is provided; to check the unintended gaps; and to watch each area of learning which can be covered in sufficient depth. It is linked to long-term plan. It can provide and frames the opportunities for two level of progress for all pupils. It focuses on specific aspects of progression and it is to cover around suitable objectives and assessment outcomes. It provides a coherent and engaging sequence for learning and teaching. It allows the learning in a meaningful context for pupils. It gives a roof for the learners to get a meaningful context for pupils. It provides planned opportunities to develop pupils' experience and understanding of key concepts.

Short- Term Plan

The set of principles on the lessons such as building, practicing, and applying skills; learning process; and progression through levels and leading to independence. A successful medium-term plan will get in the result of a short-term plan and its functions. The short-term plan has the personalization and its understanding of how the short-term will aid progression. In this short-term, the skills are essential to building through teaching-learning, application, practice and development. It explores the purpose of the skills, aims, processes, ideas and key questions.

An example

The college education has taken as an example for the three long-term, medium-term and short-term curriculum. It is the mixture of these three. The full course of Under Graduate or Post Graduate curriculum is long-term education; the yearly curriculum is called a short-term curriculum, and the short-term curriculum is the semester syllabus or term syllabus. In some of the institutions or courses, they do not have semester syllabus. In this type of courses, the term syllabus is considered a short-term curriculum. Following this, every institution has a hidden curriculum which gives the direct or indirect impact on individual learning.

Hidden Curriculum

Normally curriculum is contextually shaped to focus on the interaction to bring out the significance of a context. In this context, the learners have their examination and social relationship with their peers and the nature of the teacher-student relationship, the organization with their peers and the organization of classes and streaming. John Dewey refers to a term 'collateral learning' and its attitude which occurs in colleges. Likely defines about 'hidden curriculum'. The things which the learners are learning along with the institutional plans and organized matters and its involvement are included in the planning or those responsible for the college arrangements. This 'hidden curriculums' emphasizes on regimentation on bell and time managements and on the streaming the learners to prepare

young people. The word 'hidden' never means a negative word in 'hidden curriculum'. It is potentially liberating the learning which can enable the students to develop socially valued knowledge and skills or to form a peer group on their own and subcultures. These peer groups may contribute to personal and collective autonomy to challenge the existing norms and institutions. So these hidden curricula should be recognized appropriately and treating curriculum as a contextual social process. Through this, it is easy to get a better grasp of the impact of structural and students. These collaborations can make development and discussions on economic and gender relations. Thus the formal and informal way of the curriculum is also there to affect the learners' education.

Curriculum in Formal and Informal Education

Cornbleth, Jeff and Smith make an argument that curriculum cannot be taken out of context which should be formed with the college context. The curriculum theory and practice have to be considered with the notion like the class teacher, course, lesson and so on. When the context is altered the process is also altered. So the informal form of community work and their main impact is to formalize signified aspects of the work. Rowntree suggests these informal approaches. In informal or insightful approaches to the content of the curriculum specification Rowntree includes some examples:

Reviewing one's knowledge of the prescribed subject.

Discussing with other subject teachers or subject experts.

Analyzing similar courses elsewhere

Reading more advanced books or scholarly articles on the subjects.

Asking the students what they like to include in the subject content.

Discussing with students their existing conception of and attitude to the subject matter.

Thinking of essential activities that students need to be engaged in as part of the course.

Preparing for an examination in a syllabus through the previous year question papers, and examiners' reports and so on.

The main outcome of the curriculum is health promotion, pre-specified activities, visiting workers, regular meeting and so on. Formal education means an appropriate time for them to mount courses and to discuss content and methods in curriculum terms. In the formal curriculum, the design starts with learner's goal. It is used to derive content entitled in the functional approaches. One of the most debatable matters in course planning is in the use of objectives. In the field of common education, the use of objectives and its performance needs to be seen in a socio-political and educational context. It aims to develop knowledge and aesthetic sensibility. When a learner-centred curriculum is designed the course objectives will provide some benefits.

- Learners get more realistic ideas of what they had learned in the course.
- Language learners can earn a sensitive role and they become sharper.
- The learners get self-evaluation ideas.
- The classroom activities will be related to learners' real-life needs.

- The development of skills has also increased.

In the content designing Disick and Mager talks about the task statement which specifies what the learner is required to do. The focus of the task can vary which may be according to the socio-political status and educational context. Some examples for the tasks are the grammatical focus, functional focus, macro-skill focus, learning skill focus, cognitive focus, cultural focus, and topical focus.

- **Grammatical Focus** will concentrate on the students use on ‘Wh’ questions in the controlled drill.
- **Functional Focus** will concentrate on expressions like agreement or disagreement.
- **Macro-skill** focus concentrates in the identification of the main point in a spoken text.
- **Learning Skills** Focus is to monitor and rate the student’s performance.
- **Cognitive Focus** deals with grasping knowledge and to deliver in various innovative ways.
- **Cultural Focus** has to compare the cultural knowledge among the other cultures. It makes the students do a cultural study.
- **Topical Focus** gives attention to the learners’ obtained information about public transport.

In the functional syllabus, the tasks are different according to draw together under a particular statement. It provides a more coherent framework in specified syllabus than is provided by the general functional syllabus. The curriculum has some principles to follow while it has designed.

Principles of Curriculum and Instruction

Effective teaching blends the art and the sciences of teaching. Some effective instruction is essential for the curriculum. Effective instruction is guided by general pedagogical approaches and specific instructional practices. It occurs when the teacher links sound curriculum development and excellent instructional practice is a successful learning experience. Instructional judgment must be encouraged and nurtured in classrooms. So that learners acquire flexibility which is needed to adopt the instructional practice. This practice will meet a wide variety of students’ needs. In curriculum instructional design the curriculum designer should consider the content, perspective and processes specified. The designer should be encouraged to extend their range of instructional approach and theoretical knowledge, and a regard for students as active participants in the learning process.

Curriculum Processes

The virtues of localized curriculum development are acknowledged by classroom practitioners, program administrators continued to behave a centralized system. Curriculum planning as a systematic attempt of the curriculum cannot be done in a single sitting. As earlier told it is a development by a look at several different models and it is to develop to specify and assist in the planning, presentation and evaluation of learning. It is an attempt to see and specify what should happen at the classroom, and to reconcile the differences between what is ‘is’ and what ‘should be’. Tyler in her best-known work, “Basic Principles

of Curriculum and instruction” was published in 1949. He asserts the development of any curriculum for any subject will be based on the consideration of four fundamental questions. They follow as:

1. What educational purpose should an institutional seek to attain?
2. What educational experiences can be provided that is likely to attain the purpose?
3. How can these educational experiences be effectively organized?
4. How can we determine whether their purposes are being attained?

While analyzing these questions a curriculum developer should consider some basic things. To the first question, the developer would classify the nature of the educational enterprise in which he/she involved. The second question relates to verifying the post – syllabus’s aim and output. The curriculum designer has to get the idea of these issues. In the third question, the educational experiences can be effective by organizing the educational experiences and its stages of attaining the success of a syllabus. For the final question, the curriculum designer or the researcher should concentrate on the area of evaluation. In this, the designer should analyze the students’ performance and their output on learning the curriculum.

In Stenhouse’s view, the curriculum should have three main parts such as planning, empirical study and justification. In the planning section the planning consists of some sorts of principles in content selection, developments of teaching strategies (learn and teach), diagnose the strength and weakness of the individual student. An empirical study, the designer should concentrate in on which is to study by the students to progress them as well as for the teachers also. The designer should concentrate on what the teacher should study and guide them to implement the curriculum in various school, college, polytechnic and engineering level. The designer should give the variability of effects in handling different students and in different situations and the various students learning ability. The designer should have the ability to justify their curriculum and its aim or intention of it. He or she should have the ability to scrutiny it. Clark says the objectives should relate the skills in transactional language and easy to operate. Following those Richards discovers that the addition of new materials gives way to modify the curriculum and its objectives, learning arrangements and evaluations.

Curriculum Design in Tamil Nadu, India

In India to improve the momentum of educational quality of higher education various inspection committees are introduced by the government. The authorities like UGC, AICTE, QCI, DEC, and BCI are involved in the higher education system. The Indian Educational System of today’s purpose of learning and the purpose of education has questions. Now-a-days the old syllabus completion is challenging in nurturing the students of various level of learning and their abilities in the classroom. Multi-level discussions are going on in between policy makers, school leaders and educational consultants. The main problem faced by the policy makers is the practical way to do it. As technology enters in the entire field, a change is needed in Indian Educational System also. The impact of technology has its strengths and weaknesses. To use the virtual reality the curriculum should give its own way.

In India all states are having the freedom to initiate more educational policies in their states. Apart from Union Education minister, The Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE) is the higher advisory board to advise the central and state governments. As of 2012, India 152 central universities, 312 state universities and 191 private universities. Tamil Nadu has the privilege of being one of the most developed states in the country in the field of higher education. In Tamil Nadu, the Directorate of Collegiate Education was carved in the year 1965. Through this board the educationist develop the curriculum to offer the diversity and flexibility to learners. They redesign, restructure the curriculum to the relevant regional and national needs. The Directorate Collegiate of Education insists and collects feedback from students, alumni, faculty community and employees. It organizes training programs in effectiveness in teaching learning process. It gives total autonomy to be given to colleges as per UGC guidelines.

As per the norms 20 Government Colleges, 60 Government Aided Colleges and 7 Self-Finance Colleges have been granted Autonomous Status. In National level, for the university stage, the Ministry of education makes arrangements to bring out many low priced books with the collaboration of USA, USSR and UK. NCERT produces many books with the help of the scholars from all over the country. By the effort of national level each state is setting an expert section to make text books. The evaluation of the text book is organized by the State Educational Departments. In the field of English text-books, central Institute of English and Foreign Languages, Hyderabad and NCERT had done a lot of improvement.

While there are many formats for curriculum designing most of the curriculum/syllabus has some basic elements. They are the title of the *Curriculum/Syllabus*; time required to complete the curriculum; list of Objectives, which may be *Behavioural Objective or Knowledge Objectives*; an instructional component; allow the students to have *Undependable Practice /Independent Practice*; a clear *Summary* to help the teachers; *Evaluation Component* to test the students' mastery over the instructed skills or concepts; *Analysis Component* which is used by the teacher to test the reflection on the curriculum; and a *Continuity Component* which make reviews on the previous curriculum and reflection on the current curriculum.

Conclusion

Analyzing these curriculum methods of researchers, Indian Education System and Tamil Nadu education policies it is easy to define that the curriculum designers should have a clear idea on the students' educational level, previous learned ability, well thematic objectives, and a good evaluation method to test the mastery of the students. In English Language Teaching, the designers' personal views have included in content selection in the unit plan, and lesson plan. As per Tamil Nadu Curriculum Policy, National Educational System and UGC, the curriculum should have specific objectives; timelines for each subject and each unit; the proper and appropriate textbooks should be provided to the teachers and students. Extra books relative text materials are also should be prescribed; the designer should have the idea of evaluating the students' performance. And it should be measured in a proper way like grading or marks; and these evaluation methods should support students'

current need, skill and knowledge base, and the higher level of thinking; the curriculum should make possibilities for the next level of curriculum designing.

References:

- [1] Chaube, S.N. Curriculum Planning and Instruction. New Delhi: Wisdom Press, 2011.
- [2] Edwards, Richard (Ed). Improving Learning in College. London: Routledge, 2009.
- [3] Rani, Swarupa,T (Ed). Educational measurement and Evaluation. New Delhi: Discovery Publishing, 2006.
- [4] Nunan, David. The Learner –Centred Curriculum. UK: Cambridge University Press, 1997.
- [5]<http://edtechreview.in/trends-insights/trends/3466-industry-4-0-and-indian-education-system>
- [6]<https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/12-changes-to-get-students-job-ready-1023612-2017-07-11>
- [7] https://www.academia.edu/9139804/Designing_a_Language_Learning_Syllabus
- [8] http://www.tnuniv.ac.in/education_policy.html

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